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INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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This report builds further on deliverable D2.4 by adding the progress during project year 3 on the rollout of the pilot focus groups.

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INTRODUCTION

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

ENLIGHT is a European University Alliance to promote equitable quality of life, sustainability and global engagement through Higher Education Transformation. ENLIGHT brings together nine comprehensive research-intensive universities from nine European countries.

ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Programme and more specifically within the Science With and For Society (SWAFS) Work Programme. The ENLIGHT RISE project (Research and Innovation agenda with and for society) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT Alliance. In synergy with ENLIGHT's educational components and surrounding ecosystems, ENLIGHT RISE will deploy a comprehensive joint transformation agenda for our universities.

The main objective of Work Package 2 (WP2) of ENLIGHT RISE is to **create synergies through R&I capacity building**. Complementing the mapping of expertise in the ENLIGHT Think Tank (Erasmus+), WP2 analyses the alliance members' scientific and technological profiles and tries to exploit the synergies leading to maximize ENLIGHT Alliance's competitive advantage (task 2.1). WP2 Research & Innovation Observatory will help identifying ENLIGHT R&I capacities (task 2.2) and WP2 Pilot Focus Groups will lead the strategic orientation for building competitive R&I collaborations among them (task 2.3). At the same time, WP2 Pilot Focus Groups will help Work Package 1 ("Establish a sustainable business model towards a collaborative R&I agenda") prioritize R&I support activities.

In order to drive competitive joint Research & Innovation initiatives on flagship challenges¹ within the alliance, the ENLIGHT RISE WP2 is working to establish some pilot focus groups on ENLIGHT flagship challenges. These groups will coordinate the emergence and/or expansion of collaborative R&I actions within ENLIGHT and establish an action plan for prioritizing pilot projects and funding applications in their specific domain, in close interaction with the R&I Support Group (R&I-SG)² (WP1 Establish a sustainable business model towards a collaborative R&I agenda).

This document represents deliverable *D16 (D2.8) and is to be considered as the final update of the original D11 (D12 was a first update). It describes the outcome and achievements of the pilot focus groups by the end of the ENLIGHT RISE project lifespan, leading towards the final conclusion of this pilot initiative.*

In order to provide a complete overview of the pilot initiative, this concluding document starts from the text of D11 and D12 (the plain text in black). The specific additions to the original text (i.e. the actual text of D16) is the in blue italics.

¹ Flagship areas: Health and Well-Being; Digital revolution; Climate action; Energy transition & Circular Economy; Equity. For more information, please consult this page: <https://enlight-eu.org/university-about-us/flagship-domains> :

² The R&I-SG is a working group of research support officers from all nine universities which aims at identifying synergies that can be achieved in different sources of EC funding; facilitating/incentivizing research collaborations.

1. THE ENLIGHT RISE FOCUS GROUPS

Guidelines for the ENLIGHT RISE Focus Groups have been set up in order to give the main information on the aim, thematics, composition, expected tasks and outcomes of the Focus Groups.

AIM OF THE FOCUS GROUPS

The overall objective of these Focus Groups is to **coordinate the emergence and expansion of mission-oriented R&I projects, building on the ENLIGHT alliance R&I capacities and leading to successful grant applications around the flagship challenges.**

This main goal can be decoupled in some specific action lines that will guide the Focus Groups activity:

- ✓ Community building: getting to know each other, the different expertise available in relation to the flagship domain at each institution, and the interest for establishing collaborations;
- ✓ Identification of the right expertise at each university and facilitate the connection between them;
- ✓ Establishment of an action plan for prioritizing pilot projects and funding applications; and
- ✓ Activation of pilot R&I projects on flagship domains.

THEMATIC AREAS

The ENLIGHT alliance focuses its action around five big challenges that are key determinants of societal well-being and sustainability (ENLIGHT flagships):

- **Health and Well-being:**
Urban Health with a special focus on (i) the impact of aging populations, especially on brain and mental health, (ii) the impact of environmental exposures and inequalities in healthcare access, and (iii) opportunities for future cities through precision medicine and digital public health.
- **Digital Revolution and Impact of digitization:**
AI for Good in our cities and communities, with a special focus on digital simulation to support decision-making, AI and health, AI and sustainable society.
- **Climate change:**
Climate change and urban development with a special focus on: (i) impact of climate change on land use, socio-ecosystems, relation between cities and surrounding rural areas, (ii) mitigation through improved environmental impact assessment, intersectoral initiatives for climate neutrality.
- **Energy and Circular Economy:**
Energy conversion and transition with a special focus on multidisciplinary approaches to (i) energy transition, (ii) circularity, and (iii) raw material value chain.
- **Equity:**
Addressing polarization in our cities and communities, with a special focus on (i) urban development and marginalization, (ii) access and equity in future cities for long-term sustainability, (iii) sustainable heritage and polarization.

The ENLIGHT RISE Focus Groups will correspond to this thematic division meaning there will be five Focus Groups, one for each of the ENLIGHT Flagships.

COMPOSITION

1. Procedure for the composition of the Focus Groups

The Focus Groups' members are nominated by the universities according to their profile and qualifications, which should be relevant to the competences of the flagship domain and aligned with the following profile description.

The composition may evolve depending on the need for more specific expertise, skills and/or interest for collaboration.

2. The focus group member profile

The Focus Groups are ideally composed by a variety of profiles that will enrich the co-creation process, including (among others) the following ones:

Scientific profiles: Researchers at different stages of career having expertise in the thematic areas of the five ENLIGHT flagship areas, more specifically:

- ✓ Senior researchers specialized in a theme linked to the focus group specific flagship domain (from R3 (Established Researcher) to R4 (Leading Researcher), as defined by Euraxess research profile descriptors³); and
- ✓ Junior researchers with any background that could contribute to any of the flagship areas (R2 (Recognised Researcher, i.e. PhD holders or equivalent who are not yet fully independent)).

Research and Support staff profiles:

- ✓ One to two ENLIGHT universities' research support officers (RSOs) per focus group. These RSOs may be also part of the ENLIGHT R&I Support Group.

3. Additional recommendations to be considered for the composition of the focus groups

- ✓ Gender balance should be encouraged;
- ✓ One to two researcher representatives per university per group (ideally one junior and one senior researcher according to the definition set above in section 2);
- ✓ In the light of the synergies and complementarities between the ENLIGHT Erasmus+ and ENLIGHT RISE initiatives, the participation of researchers already members of ENLIGHT Erasmus+ Core Groups is welcome;
- ✓ Each Focus Group should be research and innovation-based.

³ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/europe/career-development/training-researchers/research-profiles-descriptors>

EXPECTED TASKS

Members of the focus groups are expected to carry out the following (non-exhaustive) list of tasks:

- ✓ **Participation in, and when decided so, coordination of a Focus Group;**
- ✓ **Identify and encourage research and innovation collaborations within the ENLIGHT alliance context:**
 - Share and exchange expertise in R&I in the flagship domains;
 - Initiate R&I initiatives in the flagship field at the local university level;
 - Identify new research collaborations.
- ✓ **Undertake R&I project collaborations:**
 - Share and exchange R&I opportunities;
 - Identify relevant calls for proposals;
 - Develop innovative collaborative research projects, involving a minimum of 3 ENLIGHT universities;
 - Develop bottom-up collaborations.
- ✓ **Define and update a road map for each group;**
- ✓ **Foster synergies and complementarities with ENLIGHT education and training activities;**
- ✓ **Liaise with ENLIGHT Erasmus+ think tank (see section below “Action plan/ links with Erasmus+ Core Groups) in terms of new research opportunities, collaborations and priorities for local partners.**

RECOMMENDED OPERATIVE FRAMEWORK

- ✓ During the first months, it is expected that the members of each group will meet once a month to get to know each other, identify relevant initiatives for collaboration and be able to propose a road map for the group.
- ✓ Each focus group will be led by a leading trio with rotating coordination. The leading trio will be nominated during the first meetings of the group.
- ✓ The focus group will count with managerial and administrative support by the ENLIGHT RISE WP2 team.

OUTPUTS

During the first round of the Focus Groups there are three main expected outputs:

- **Draft road map.** The focus group members will jointly initiate and develop a road map for their group;
- **Short list of complementary research themes.** The focus groups will identify common research topics/ priorities and sub-topics/ priorities to drive joint collaborations/ proposals;
- **External funding opportunities.** The focus groups will identify and should respond to at least one research and innovation call for proposals.

2. ACTION PLAN

As detailed above, each focus group will propose its road map to prioritize and develop its own actions. Each group will have to describe its action plan, the ambition and the planned activities. A template will be proposed to them containing the following items:

- **Action description:**
 - o summary, expected impact and results, complementarity/expertise of partners;
 - o Innovative and strategic aspects of the action;
 - o Long-term goals and sustainability of the cooperation;
 - o European/International call identified (if any) & deadline foreseen.
- **Reverse Schedule;**
- **Expected and Desired Impact on ENLIGHT Flagships/Europe/Society.**

Links with Erasmus+ CORE GROUPS and THINK TANK

In order to reinforce synergies and complementarities between the education and the research and innovation components of the ENLIGHT alliance, a foreseen development and sustainability element for the focus groups is to use the existing ENLIGHT Erasmus+ Think Tank structure. The ENLIGHT Erasmus+ Think Tank is a space for innovation and interconnecting know-how in the flagship domains. It is an inter-university sharing platform regrouping the Erasmus+ core groups (education component of the Alliance) across the nine universities. It enables the members to share the data and milestones of their flagship domain and to identify transversal topics within the flagship areas.

The Think Tank would be then seen as an umbrella for both the education and research and innovation components of the ENLIGHT alliance, enabling the exchange of information, synergies and complementarities with the two independent subgroups (the Core Groups and the Focus Groups) per thematic area.

3. ROLLOUT OF THE FOCUS GROUPS

COMPOSITION AND CREATION

With the publication of D11 in M24, the guidelines for the pilot focus groups (FGs) had been set and thus the attention switched towards the composition and start of the FGs.

Deviating from the General Agreement (GA), WP2 esteemed it best to immediately create five FGs (one per flagship domain) instead of starting only with one on 'health & well-being' and subsequently an additional two on 'climate change' and 'energy & circular economy', as foreseen in the GA. With the finality to foster new R&I collaborations and work towards joint project proposals at the end of project year 3, WP2 considered it best to create all 5 FGs as soon as possible for its members to have the maximum amount of time possible to grow towards joint collaborations.

At the start of project year 2 all partner institutions were asked to seek or nominate their institutional representatives for each FG. More specifically, each partner university (PU) was asked to delegate to

each FG 1 senior and 1 junior researcher in the specific field of interest of the FG, along with 1 research support (RS) administrator. To secure the connection with the R&I Support Group (R&I-SG) created in WP1, it was advised to appoint as the RS administrator an active member of WP1 and/or the R&I-SG.

PU's approached this question in different ways; while some PU's nominated for each FG the same members as for the Core Groups of the ENLIGHT E+ programme to keep a general overview and connection, others launched an internal call for candidates, whilst still others approached and nominated specific researchers directly. Most, if not all, administrative staff delegated to the FGs are either the PU's ENLIGHT RISE institutional contact point/programme manager, or indeed the PU's (thematic) member of WP1 and/or the R&I-SG.

Due to the different nomination processes, finalizing the composition of the FGs took several months and was but completed by December 2022 (M28) upon which doodles were sent out to gather a first (online) meeting. This led to all 5 FGs celebrating their kick-off meeting in January 2023 (M29). Since, and prior to the 2023 summer recess, all 5 FGs have held multiple meetings.

As a result, 5 thematic pilot focus groups have already been created (i.e. 2 more and 2 years earlier than projected in the GA). During the first months, all 5 FGs have focussed their attention on getting to know each other and each other's research interests, defining the specific focus of the thematic FG, and starting up thematic subgroups.

What follows, is an account of each FG's activities and workplan, followed by a general conclusion and listing of interim takeaways.

OVERVIEW AND MODUS OPERANDI OF THE FOCUS GROUPS

All FGs celebrated their individual kick-off meeting in January 2023 in a similar way.

After a general presentation by the WP2 lead on the intent and expectations of the pilot focus groups, all FGs debated on how to progress and to decide on which research fields to focus. With each flagship domain being very broad and only vaguely defined (i.e., containing a huge variety of different research fields/topics) all 5 FGs initially felt the need to clearly define their focus/working theme of interest.

Considering that almost all FG members did not meet each other earlier, the need was felt to create a clear view on the expertise (project track record, research focus, and expectations) of all FG members. Thereto, a flagship area specific participant profile template was created for all FG participants to fill out (cf. Annex 1 – template participant profile as created for the FG on climate change). Since the FG members are considered representatives of their home institutions' research community for the entire research field linked to the flagship area, the participant profile also inquired into the PU's focus areas and specific expertise on the flagship domain overall.

The goal was that information obtained through these profiles would surface possible linkages and automatically indicate which research topics the FG should/could focus on to start up new research collaborations amongst the ENLIGHT PU's.

This however did not concretize in all FGs; for some it worked and served as a roadmap towards selecting a focal topic, other FGs sought a different way to determine their central topic(s) and way forward.

Below an account is given on the activities and main decisions taken per FG with respect to the roadmap/action plan and the way ahead:

Focus Group on Climate Change

The FG kicked off January 26th, 2023, and met on June 1st, 2023, for the fourth time.

The filled-out participant profiles proved insufficient to draw workable conclusions, partly because the questionnaire was filled out too personal by the researchers (i.e., focussing on their own research (interests)) and not from an institutional point of view, leading to too diverse and specific research fields which did not allow to detect broad/general commonalities.

The FG therefore decided to relaunch the exercise by asking each PU to identify a maximum of 5 research topics of interest (\approx priorities) for their research community on which they would like to engage into joint research collaboration with the other ENLIGHT PUs. The received topics were then put into a spreadsheet for each PU to indicate which of the stated research field they have interested researchers for within their own institution. The idea was that this would make it possible to identify – within the broad field of the flagship area – specific research topics to investigate probable collaboration efforts between PUs.

With the help of the (WP1) R&I-SG, this spreadsheet was expanded with a list of upcoming and foreseen Horizon Europe calls. PUs were asked to discuss this list internally and indicate whether their research community bears researchers interested in engaging into possible project proposal writing efforts for one or more of these calls.

The spreadsheet did not miss its effect and outlaid possible topics for collaboration. Based on its outcomes, 2 subgroups have been created: one on “aerosol-cloud interactions” and another on “development of climate services”. These subgroups are being led by one FG researcher per subgroup who will set up (online) meetings inviting all PUs to send their interested researchers to these meetings to discuss and examine possibilities for joint research collaborations on the specific topic, and investigate the probability to engage into a joint research proposal within the near future.

A next FG meeting will be held in October to examine the progress and viability of the subgroups and assess whether additional subgroups could be created based on the information in the spreadsheet and/or whether a different approach for different focus research topics should be adopted/sought.

The spreadsheet will remain as a database of the thematic interests for collaborations per PU in the flagship domain.

During the ENLIGHT RISE project lifespan, the “FG Climate” met, in total, seven times. Though the creation of the subgroups seemed a logic step at first, both subgroups struggled to secure sufficient interest from a PI/leading researcher, leading to the decision to no longer pursue the creation of the subgroups.

Alongside, and partially because the difference between the FGs on ‘Climate’ and on ‘Energy and circular economy’ proved negligible and some researchers “transferred” to the FG ‘Energy’, the attendance of this FG’s meetings declined.

Nevertheless, information was widely spread amongst the integrant of the FG Climate by sending around interesting news, calls for partners, funding opportunities, announcements of conference, workshops etc amount. More than the meetings themselves, the mailing list of PU's key researchers on this topic seemed a way of bridging the gap between the various research communities.

Considering the growing difficulty of setting a date for new meetings, and – moreover – the fact that mostly only administrative support staff attended, and the fact that important and interesting news circulated via the mailing list, no further need was felt to organise meetings.

In the final meeting, partners acknowledged the spreadsheet as a sound and useful archive of thematic interests of each partner's research community for future (ENLIGHT) collaborations. Overall, they evaluated the pilot focus group as valid exercise and “a bridge to getting to know counterparts” within the other ENLIGHT universities, specifying that research contacts had been established.

In conclusion, although the focus group will no longer meet on a periodical basis, the contact list remains and interesting news, calls for interest, conferences, etc. are still (and in the future will still be) sent around to the people on the list.

The FG in that sense did not cease to exist but went into hibernation, with a meeting being able to be called upon by any member whenever new calls or other opportunities arise. Any researcher can call for a meeting by contacting rise@ugent.be.

Focus Group on Digital Revolution and Impact of Digitization

With a kick-off meeting on January 9th, 2023, the FG “Digital” met for the third time on June 5th, 2023.

During the second FG meeting, and based on the participant profiles, three focus areas were selected: ‘Robotics’, ‘Cybersecurity’, and ‘Extended reality’. Three researchers volunteered to set up a topic specific meeting with colleagues from other PUs to investigate potential joint collaborations on these topics.

Alongside, the FG members were attracted by the programme of the European Dialogue & AIMDay on the topic of digital health, jointly organized by the ENLIGHT RISE WP5 and ENLIGHT E+ WP5 and scheduled for May 25th, 2023, in Galway. The FG decided 1) that some members would attend this event to investigate potential opportunities, and 2) that a next meeting would be postponed until after the event.

The third FG meeting highlighted that the AIMDay disclosed some potential for collaborations on digital health and extended reality in psychology. Individual researchers will follow this up and perhaps take contact with the FG Health & Well-being since there appear to be many influences and points of contact between the FG “Digital” and the FG “Health”. To that purpose a Discord environment has been set up to rapidly exchange information amongst the members of the FG “Digital”.

Concerning the three subgroups, insufficient potential was found regarding ‘extended reality’. The other two subgroups still have to meet for the first time.

Considering the above, and the diminishing interest and attendance at this FG, the members decided to engage into bilateral contacts and to postpone a next meeting of the FG “Digital” until November-December 2023 to then assess what came out of the bilateral contacts and to reassess possibilities for joint research collaborations.

The “FG Digital” met, in total, five times during the ENLIGHT RISE project lifespan and never really progressed away from the bilateral contacts. These, however, resulted in sound cooperations and actions e.g. the Tartu University and the Groningen University whom started up joint research and teaching efforts, and the University of Bordeaux submitting a national BAIA proposal together with various ENLIGHT partner universities.

In its last meeting, the FG decided to dissolve and no longer meet. Main reason given, was the vastness and extensive subtopics of the digital topic, and its researchers, which did not really create that many points of contact between the FG members.

Here as well, however, interesting thematic info is still being shared through the mailing list.

Focus Group on Energy and Circular Economy

Starting with its kick-off on January 24th, 2023, the FG has met a fourth time on May 15th, 2023.

FG “Energy” has followed a similar path as FG “Climate” in the sense that it also created a spreadsheet to outlay potential links for cooperation based on PU’s main topics of interest and their specific interest regarding existing and foreseen Horizon Europe calls.

This exercise identified 4 clusters of linked research themes with sufficient interest of PUs, leading to the creation of 2 subgroups: one on “Energy storage and production with prime focus on hydrogen”, and another on “Environmental innovations and circular economy, LCA”. Separate meetings will be organized by these subgroups before the end of September 2023 to study concrete possibilities for collaboration.

Regarding the remaining two topics “Positive energy districts” and “Nature based solutions for buildings” already 2 ENLIGHT consortia (respectively ‘E-PED’ and ‘NB²E’) had been created through the [Ghent University Call for ENLIGHT Scientific Research Networks](#). These consortia will proceed with their preparations for 2 project proposals each and will – through the FG “Climate” – invite the remaining PUs to join the proposal once its framework is more concrete.

The FG will meet again in October 2023 to discuss the progress on each of the themes/subgroups.

The “FG Energy” gathered eight times along the ENLIGHT RISE project lifespan.

It invested quite some time and effort in its spreadsheet which now provides a blueprint of possible collaborations linked to related Horizon Europe calls.

Many linkages were consolidated, and through the cooperation with and within the aforementioned UGent financed consortia, 2 Horizon Europe proposals were submitted.

DISRUPT ME (UBx (Lead), UGent, UGOE, UT, UG -> linked to E-PED) was not rewarded, but the WOOD-STOCK proposal (UGent (lead), UBx, GAL -> via the NB²E consortium) was selected and will start as a remunerated Horizon Europe project (call: HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-01-05).

The subgroup “Energy storage and production with prime focus on hydrogen” offered a successful pitching session during the online matchmaking event organized by WP1 (April 29th, 2024), see Deliverable D8-D1.8. The outcome thereof was the creation of an ENLIGHT network on Hydrogen preparing

a proposal for the ENLIGHT2.0 call for Thematic Networks, with the clear intention of consolidating a Hydrogen hub within ENLIGHT.

Reflecting on the end of the ENLIGHT RISE project funding and the initiative of the pilot focus group on the flagship “energy and circular economy”, partners in the last meeting acknowledge the spreadsheet as a sound and useful archive of thematic interest of each partner's research community for future (ENLIGHT) collaboration. It is to be considered as the heritage of the focus group and a resource to be consulted every time new HE calls are launched.

Alike the FG Climate, ‘Energy’ recognized a) the pilot initiative as valid and “a bridge to getting to know counterparts” within the other ENLIGHT universities, and b) that specific research contacts had been established. FG Energy, too, decided to go into hibernation and only further meet upon the explicit call therefore by one of the members. Meanwhile, interesting novelties, calls, etc. are circulated and sent to all members on the contact list.

Focus Group on Equity

After its first meeting on January 12th, 2023, FG Equity has met a second time on the 23rd of March 2023.

The FG first sought on how to define the scope of/on equity but agreed on its delimitation through the general description of the flagship domain's key themes on the ENLIGHT website (<https://www.enlight-eu.org/university-about-us/flagship-domains>).

The participant profiles and the received list of institutional focus topics did indeed demonstrate potential and viable interest to start up joint research collaboration, and the idea was launched/accepted to work towards 1 specific Horizon Europe call: HORIZON-CL2-2024-DEMOCRACY-01-04: The interrelation between social, cultural, and political identities, as well as the sense of belonging, and democracies.

The FG discussed whether to start the FG activities with one overall transdisciplinary topic, two sub-themes, or whether to work with small groups working out ideas and afterwards bringing concrete concepts for proposals into the general focus group meeting. The FG finally decided to create two subgroups focussing on: 1. environmental transition policies and social justice, and 2. identity, belonging and interrelation between social culture and political identities in democracy.

Since this second meeting (March 23rd, 2023) the FG has not met again, however both subgroups are working separately investigating possible project proposals. A follow-up general meeting will be held in September 2023.

Although the FG Equity only met six times during the ENLIGHT RISE project lifespan, it has undoubtedly been the most productive pilot focus group in terms of submitted project proposals so far.

The subgroup “Identity, belonging and interrelation between social culture and political identities in democracy” submitted 3 Horizon Europe project proposals to the call “HORIZON-CL2-2024-DEMOCRACY-01”, of which one has been granted, and another has been ranked second on the reserve list:

1. EMMELO (European Men, Masculinity, and Extremist Leadership Online)

- ENLIGHT Universities participating: Gal (Lead), UGOE, UU, and UBx
- granted
- 2. G-ENGAGE (*Learning from feminist protest politics against the far right to restore (young) citizens' trust in electoral institutions: an intersectional gender perspective*)
 - (ENLIGHT Universities participating: Gal (lead), UU, UBx
 - Second on the reserve list
- 3. FFluidD (*Fostering Sense of Belonging and Trust for Fluid Identities in Democracies*)
 - ENLIGHT Universities participating: Gal (Lead), UGOE, UU, UT, UBx
 - Not granted

On top of these submitted proposals, the subgroup organised (June 20th, 2024) the online workshop “The trouble with identity and belonging: What do we talk about when we talk about identity?” supported by and with active participation from Gal, UBx, UGOE, UGent.

During the workshop, the possibility was discussed to apply to the ENLIGHT2.0 ETN call for thematic networks. Interest was/is high but the timing was too short (application date June 30th, 2024). Hence the workgroup decided to apply to next year's call. The group will thereto meet in October 2024 to start preparing its 2025 application.

Worthwhile mentioning is that this subgroup sprouts out of the ENLIGHT network DEMOGLOBE (*Future of Democracies' Transformations in Europe and Across the Globe*) supported through funding obtained via the University of Galway institutional call for ENLIGHT networks.

Though the subgroup “environmental transition policies and social justice” did not effectively kick-off, the linked ENLIGHT MULTISET research network (*Multisolving for Sustainability and Equity Transitions*; <https://ssrc.ie/multiset/>) – also being supported by funding obtained through the University of Galway institutional call for ENLIGHT networks – submitted 1 proposal to HE call project proposals and is working on 2 more to be submitted to a later call:

1. MULTISET (*Focus on multilevel governance: multi-solving for sustainable and equitable transitions.*)
 - Partners: UG (lead), UU, UBx
 - not granted
2. REaLT (*Recovering the educational and learning dimensions of transdisciplinarity*)
 - will submit to the October 2024 call for ERC SYNERGY
3. Workgroup without clear name around Prof. Kevin Leyden is working out a proposal to be submitted in an upcoming HE democracy call.

After a very intensive and productive 2023-2024, the pilot focus group decided not to further schedule any group meetings, and instead – alike other focus groups – go into hibernation and use the contact list to disperse interesting thematic news, calls, workshops, etc.

However, the subgroup “Identity, belonging and interrelation between social culture and political identities in democracy” will continue to meet in order to prepare a project proposal for the ENLIGHT 2.0 ETN call expected to be launched the first months of 2025.

Focus Group on Health and Well-being

The FG kicked-off on January 23rd, 2023, with a fourth meeting on June 1st, 2023.

Alike the FGs “Climate Change” and “Energy”, the participant profiles did not offer a clear result on how to proceed within this FG and thus also FG “Health” launched a spreadsheet for each PU to identify their main topics of interest for joint collaborations as well as the Horizon Europe calls their research community would be interested in. This exercise is still on-going and extended towards the search for possibilities through regional/local/national funding schemes.

Nevertheless, during this process two subgroups have been created: one on “aging” and one on “nursing”. They will organize separate meetings inviting all PUs’ researchers interested in the respective topic to attend and discuss possibilities and opportunities for joint research and/or project proposals on the respective topics.

Alongside, FG “Health” has served as forum for PUs to share information on individual projects and to launch calls for partners regarding already existing project proposal writing initiatives. Also, based on the experiences during the AIMDays on Digital Health (organized by WP5), a possible link with FG “Digital” is being explored.

After summer recess 2023, the next FG meeting will follow-up on both the spreadsheet and the progress of the subgroups.

Undoubtedly, with its eight FG meetings and four subgroup meetings during the ENLIGHT RISE project lifespan, the FG “Health” has been the most active in terms of gatherings.

Both subgroups actively met on multiple occasions and have created their own communities with individual/separate repositories on the ENLIGHT RISE project SharePoint where they have created a space for members to post data sets, research outcomes, funding opportunities, calls for partners etc.

Both have succeeded in gathering researchers of different scientific backgrounds and specialisations who all, in one way or another, are linked to the topics of ‘aging’ and ‘nursing’.

The subgroup on ‘aging’ set the tone/standard by organising a first meeting which resulted in a ‘mini-conference’ where all attending researchers presented (through a standardized template) their main research focus and results. Roughly 20 researchers from all partners presented/pitched, enabling their colleagues from the other ENLIGHT research communities to create a sound idea and overview of the institutional efforts and focus of each PU on ‘aging’.

This led to a solid network/list of circa 50+ ENLIGHT ‘aging researchers’, multiple instantly outflowing collaborations, and the sharing of research datasets and results.

The success of this subgroup was assessed as largely due to the organisational modus operandi of its first (networking) meeting.

Rather than first finding interested researchers and meeting collaborators, and subsequently sending out doodles, the decision was taken to immediately circulate one general and all-including invitation throughout the entire ENLIGHT network. This message included i) a fixed date and time, ii) an invitation to all researchers working on ‘aging’ (regardless of their specialisation/research/scientific background, iii) the direct link to attend online, iv) the PowerPoint template to present/pitch own research focus and

results, v) a link to register, and vi) a link to register in case one could not attend the online meeting but would like to be informed on/included in further efforts concerning 'aging'. The dispersed invitation also mentioned that the meeting would be recorded and made accessible for those who could not attend.

We believe that the directness of the invitation, its holistic approach, and the possibility to be further included without attending the meeting, was pivotal to attract the attention of many researchers.

This *modus operandi* reduced the administrative hazard for them to a minimum, and we identify this approach as a good practice.

Besides leading to various spontaneous research contact/collaborations, the immediate outcome of this first meeting was the start-up of a project proposal leading to the submission to the Horizon Europe call "NutriBrain – ERA4Health 2024" of ANCHORS (GAL (lead), UGent, UBx, and UBern⁴).

Unfortunately, the project was not granted, but the submitting network remains active and is preparing a proposal for the expected ENLIGHT 2.0 ETN Thematic Networks call in Spring 2025.

The subgroup 'nursing' followed the example and *modus operandi* of the colleagues from "aging", and has created a vast network of 20+ nursing-related researchers. The diversity of the different research focusses of their members has, however, made it somewhat more difficult to come toward immediate results. Probably two sub-subgroups will be created to tackle this. The network thus remains active, is planning future meetings and also studies the possibility of submitting an ENLIGHT 2.0 TN proposal in Spring 2025.

The "general" FG meetings also paid much attention to the elaborations and continuous updating of the aforementioned spreadsheet. It has become a solid overview of partners' collaboration interests, linked to possibilities for Horizon Europe funding. The meetings furthermore proved to be a billboard of ongoing research efforts at the different communities, and a pinboard for call for partners.

Amongst others, this led to the submission of a proposal to the 'Health Research Charities Ireland' of a 2-year project for circa € 250K (INNEACH: Intergenerational Programmes to enhance social connectivity for people living with dementia; GAL + UGent along with other non-ENLIGHT partners). The proposal has passed the first phase of this 2-stage application and is currently waiting to the final result.

The linked ENLIGHT working groups on 'CANCER' (all ENLIGHT partners participate) and another one on 'neuroscience and Parkinson's disease' (UPV/EHS, UBx, UU UGent, UGOE) have both organised online and physical seminars/workshops and proposal writing meetings. Both are preparing a submission to the 2024 Spring ENLIGHT2.0 ETN thematic networks call.

Of all pilot focus groups, the one on health has perhaps been the one most creating a sense of community. It is therefore no surprise that this focus group has decided to remain active and meet periodically each trimester, even after the termination of the ENLIGHT RISE project. Likewise, the subgroups have decided to keep on meeting and invest time into their created community.

⁴ ENLIGHT Consortium partner who is not part of the ENLIGHT RISE project

TAKEAWAYS, CONCLUSION AND WAY FORWARD (FUTURE PROSPECTS)

After one semester of activities, all five FGs are well underway. They all have been able to define research topics to focus on. Though the road to successful and sustainable joint research collaboration is still long and uncertain and finding the suitable modus operandi for every FG proved a real quest, we consider the start-up phase successful and promising.

The activities foreseen during the first semester of project year 3 by each FG will be crucial to obtain real and effective results (e.g. submitted or ready to submit project proposals) by the end of the ENLIGHT RISE project lifespan.

Five months of trial and error during the meetings of the FGs has given us certain insights and enables us to draw preliminary conclusions on what works, what doesn't, how realistic our initial action plan for the pilot focus groups (D11) was, good practices, and no-goes. Below a list of some of the preliminary findings and deviations in the rollout of the FG according to the action plan projected in D11.

- Proposing a road map/action plan per FG did not prove realistic; FGs grow organically.
As written in the GA, Chapter 2 of D11 envisioned each FG to propose a detailed road map on their modus operandi and activities. This appeared to be too administrative, too complex, and moreover a letdown for the researchers. The road map was therefore discarded after the kick-off meeting of all FGs. Especially since most time spent in the start-up phase went into getting to know the other members of the FG. FGs function best when taking swift decisions and working by trial and error. Evidence hereof is that 3 FGs organically evolved towards the same successful modus operandi.
- Meeting once a month proved too challenging and unrealistic for most researchers.
The FG are on-top-off activities for both researchers and administrative staff. The initial plan to meet once a month turned out to be unrealistic given the complex/full agenda of most researchers. Given that the FG members are considered representatives of their PU community on the broad flagship domain, furthermore, required many of the FG members to consult internally to be able to outlay and define their PUs priorities and views. This takes time and effort and could not all be balled up in one month. Defining a date to meet already proved challenging by itself considering the packed agendas.
Meeting every 8-10 weeks in the beginning, and then later every 3 months seems more realistic.
- The envisioned rotating coordination by a leading trio proved not to be feasible.
As already mentioned, the participation of researchers and administrative staff in FGs, is mostly on-top-off and most members have a busy and stretched schedule. Although the intention for the FGs is that they are 'for and by' the researchers, it has proven almost impossible to find a researcher willing to take up the (organizational) lead of the FG. Only one researcher accepted and thus in practice all but one (FG "Equity") of the pilot focus groups have all been organized and are led by the WP2 lead. Probably the facts that chairing a meeting also costs time to prepare the meetings and that most members do not really know each other also played a role here.
- Granting protected time for community building activities related to the FG is unrealistic for most.
The ENLIGHT RISE project proposal foresaw for FG members to receive protected time to work for the FGs, and thus be acquitted of some of their tasks within their institution or to receive a (financial) incentive/benefit. Due to internal institutional regulations, this however is not possible nor

common practice in most, if not all, PUs and therefore the involvement in the FGs remains on-top-off and voluntary.

- Top-down forcing of researchers does not work well and is not productive.
The FG have been sprouted top-down whilst most (successful) research collaborations originate bottom up. This was visible during the composition phase of the FGs. It was often hard to find researchers willing to invest time in a trajectory towards a pilot project with peers they did not know and a high risk of failure. Especially since it is all on-top-off (cf. above point). Drop-out has been significant and – although possibly also related to full schedules – it has been challenging to keep researchers interested in the start-up phase when no clear result could be guaranteed.
- Researchers are unfamiliar with representing their institutional research community.
FG members are expected to represent their institutional community on the concerned flagship domain. As also experienced in the E+ Core Groups, this is often difficult for researchers/academics due to the vastness of the flagship domain (see next point) and due to the pressure of their own personal interests, needs and expectations. This results in FG participants with different starting points: while some are interested in the complete picture of the flagship domain within the PUs, others are only focussed on their own topics of interest and cannot/do not outlay the complete flagship domain picture of their institution. PUs who have RS administrators dedicated at capturing the complete blueprint of a certain domain within their institutional community tackle this by assisting their FG participant. However not all PUs have such dedicated RS administrators at their disposal.
- The flagship domains are too broad and vaguely defined.
The ENLIGHT flagship domains each represent various and different research fields making it hard for focussed researchers to have an overall overview on what is going on within their institution on all related research topics that fall under the respective flagship domain. Having researchers around the table who topic wise are not directly linked, makes it challenging for the FG to quickly identify possibilities for joint research collaboration. E.g. in the FG "Health" you might have a neurologist, paediatrician, dietitian and a dentist around the table. Not only is it hard for them to have an overview on the research conducted in the different fields, their own research is often far away from the topics studied by the other FG members. As mentioned in the point above, institutional RS administrators with a complete overview of their institutional activities can tackle this, but this is not a luxury available to all PUs.

The duality of having a broad spectrum of research specialities/backgrounds within one FG is demonstrated by the opposite experiences in FG Digital and FG Health. Whilst FG Digital could not proceed with its members' interest/focus being too far apart, this multidisciplinary is in part what contributed to the success of the subgroup 'aging' where a multifocal approach on a specific issue enriches the scope and effectiveness of the potential impact of research collaborations.

- Junior (early career) researchers are harder to involve.
Contrary to the expectations, junior researchers are less involved in the FGs. Although they are at the start of their career and we thus expected them to seize the opportunity to expand their network via the FGs, it has been harder to keep them on board. We suspect this is linked to their full

agendas and limited time since they focus mainly on their own activities to pump up their curriculum.

➤ It is not imperative for all PUs to participate to all FGs

Linked to the reasons mentioned in both previous points, and since every PU has their own research focusses, not all PUs participate to all FGs. This is widely accepted within the FGs and in a natural way limits the amount of people around the table making it sometimes easier to take quick decisions on the way forward or to decide on the research topics to be selected. It does however remain a point of attention since e.g. the FG “Digital” experienced a lack of critical mass to make any progress in its last meeting.

➤ The foreseen link with the Think Tank / E+ Core Groups is not a first priority, yet...

Time is money, especially in the stretched agendas of researchers and educators. As mentioned above, obtaining the overview on a flagship domain already requires time and effort and the FG timeline is limited. Hence, engaging with the E+ Think Tank/Core Groups is not a priority at this point and all attention is geared towards the start-up of new research collaborations.

Notwithstanding, we do still believe in the necessity and benefit of linking the Focus and the Core groups, and foresee this to happen at a later stage, as is envisioned in the follow-up E+ project proposal for ENLIGHT 2.0.

➤ The timeline of the Horizon Europe calls does not favour the FG timeline.

Listing the existing and foreseen Horizon Europe call deadlines made clear that for some topics, either the most relevant call had already been closed at the FG kick-off meeting or the deadline was too nearby to write an effective and successful project proposal considering this is a lengthy process. Notwithstanding, WP2 decided to launch at once all 5 FGs in order to tackle this issue considering much time goes into getting acquainted with the peers, reality shows that many of the upcoming deadlines in Horizon Europe (HE) are unrealistic because of the extra lengthy process needed by a consortium of partners who hardly knew each other beforehand to agree on a set of joint research activities to include in a successful project proposal to be submitted during the timeline of the RISE project.

Future HE work programmes will – of course – always be scrutinized. However, some FGs and researchers have therefore shifted their attention towards regional/national calls in order to try to submit joint proposals before M36 of the RISE project. They realise however it will be harder/impossible for other ENLIGHT PUs to become (financial) beneficiaries in those calls. This reality has made it harder to keep senior researchers interested in, and on board of, the FGs.

➤ Finding additional funding for the FG mobility looms as a future priority.

We suspect that funding for mobility will become in demand once proposal writing becomes more concrete and FG members will want to meet to advance their project.

Contrary to our initial expectations, researchers did not specifically request for travel budgets to meet. We suspect that, since COVID-19, the exploded online meeting culture has generalized to

meet online. Moreover, it proved difficult to award all available mobility awards (see deliverable D2.7-D15).

- Creating linkages takes time.
(Senior) researchers mostly have their portfolio of colleagues they collaborate with. Expecting them to swiftly go into project proposals (writing) with new (unknown) partners and researchers (sometimes perhaps involving having to omit their usual collaborators) takes confidence and thus time. This does not favour the abovementioned strict timeline of the ENLIGHT RISE project. To increase mutual trust and confidence, it may be useful for the researchers (FG members) to meet in person. We will therefore explore how to facilitate this through the Travel Awards (cf. GA task 2.3.2, page 84)
- Researchers are interested in expanding their network through the ENLIGHT consortium.
Participating researchers do show interest in a system of close partner universities with a preferred status. The level of interconnectivity and the offered research support amongst the PUs appeals. However, as mentioned above, most (senior) researchers already have a portfolio of collaborating (inter)national researchers, and creating new (research) relationships takes time.
- Links appear and function with other ENLIGHT WPs
The help of the ENLIGHT RISE WP1 R&I Support Group was vital to list the available funding calls and the experience at the ENLIGHT RISE WP5 AIMDay in Galway led to new possibilities and cross-overs between FGs. This is a clear example that the FG fit well within the general intent of the ENLIGHT RISE programme.
- The tools created by ENLIGHT (RISE) are of use to the FGs
The already existing tools created by the ENLIGHT project, and those in the pipeline, answer to many questions raised during the FG meeting, and have already proven their purpose for the FGs. We did notice however that they are still underknown by most researchers. Herein lies an opportunity and task for the FGs. We will thus vastly promote the ENLIGHT tools amongst the FG members to boost their usage and fame. Amongst others it concerns the following tools:
 - Partner search: <https://enlight-eu.org/contact/partner-search>
 - Peers search: <https://enlight-eu.org/contact/find-your-enlight-peers>
 - Expertise search: <https://enlight-eu.org/landing-research-and-innovation/r-i-observatory>
 - Digital Matching tool: to be finalized during project year 3
 - ENLIGHT repository of good practices on research impact: <https://impact.enlight-eu.org/>
 - ENLIGHT toolkit for self-assessment of universities research impact awareness, literacy and readiness: <https://impact.enlight-eu.org/self-assessment>
 - R&I Observatory: <https://observatory.enlight-eu.org/>
 - The toolkit for (young) researchers: <https://www.enlight-eu.org/landing-research-and-innovation/r-i-support-and-collaborations/726-toolkit-for-researchers>
 - Open Science ambassadors: <https://www.enlight-eu.org/landing-research-and-innovation/open-science/ambassadors>

- ENLIGHT Impact Ambassadors: <https://impact.enlight-eu.org/ambassadors>
- Mapping dashboards: on the internal SharePoint
- ENLIGHT (RISE) funding opportunities: <https://www.enlight-eu.org/landing-research-and-innovation/awards-additional-funding> & <https://www.enlight-eu.org/university-about-us/funding>

➤ The spreadsheet has proven its use and can be considered a **good practice**.

The Excel-file created for 3 FGs to quickly outlay possible linkages and possibilities for joint proposal writing was effective and helpful. Based on its outcomes, FGs were enabled to instantly view which research field they should focus their attention at (and create subgroups). As an additional advantage, they remain as a database/repository of the thematic interests for collaborations per PU in the respective flagship domains *even if or when a FG becomes less active*.

See annexes 2 and 3 for a visual outlay of the spreadsheet for FG “Climate” and FG “Energy”.

One major advantage of the spreadsheet, is that it does not require many resources; apart from the minimal labour hours, there is actually no cost at all. It has thereby proven itself as an effective low-cost mapping tool of possible research collaboration.

➤ (Internal/Institutional) Seed funding for small thematic research networks is effective

The Ghent University, the University of Galway, and the University of the Basque Country launched calls to financially support (via funds received from their national/regional governments) several thematic ENLIGHT research network. These networks, consisting of researchers from minimum three different ENLIGHT RISE PUs, not only helped closing the gap between the different research communities, moreover, they proved hotbeds for sound project proposal. The linkage of these thematic research networks and the pilot focus groups led, amongst others, to nine Horizon Europe proposals of which at this moment two have already been granted and will start up in the upcoming months.

➤ Subgroups require a strong and motivated academic frontrunner

Whereas focus groups as such can be led by RS staff, subgroups require a strong and motivated academic spearhead who puts his/her weight in on it and takes the lead. Support staff can certainly take care of the administrative and organisational work regarding the set-up of meetings, minutes etc, but the lead's level of motivation and actual desire to engage into joint collaboration is what makes the difference, attracts colleague academics and causes the spark.

➤ Once results have been achieved, it is difficult to keep the academics motivated to meet

All FGs suffered a diminish in attendance and general interest immediately after specific results had been achieved. This was especially noticeable in the FGs ‘Equity’ and ‘Energy’. Once the various efforts (i.e. project proposal, workshops) had been finalized and/or achieved, many researchers did not further attend or engage into the FG (’s meetings). This is understandable both in terms of available and invested time, though also proves the abovementioned issue that some researchers attend for (personal) quick win. Then again however, only after the acceptance/awarding of a project proposal, does the real work and time investment actually start...

➤ Focus groups can survive without meeting – contact list can take over

Linked to the above point, the gradually diminishing attendance at most FG's did not necessarily mean less joint activity and/or sharing of information. The experience shows that once connections have been established, researchers keep on informing each other on interesting topics. In that sense, holding FG meetings in many cases has been replaced by sending out e-mails with relevant information amongst the contact list of the concerned FGs. In those cases, it is advisable to have one designated RS administrator who takes on the role of receiver of the information and hatch towards the group.

Being part of a contact list enhanced the feeling of a separate (thematic) community and did bring the researchers and the various research communities closer together.

All but one FGs decided that this is the way forward and agreed not to plan any further meetings unless specifically requested by one member and/or when potentially interesting HE call have been launched.

- *Focus (sub)groups should be straightforward, clear on intent, and remove researchers' administrative burden to become **good practice**.*

The experience of the modus operandi used for the subgroup 'aging', outlays that researchers are most likely to attend and actively participate if invited at once to a finalized event. Sending out (multiple) e-mails with doodles, different e-mails with presentation templates, etc., represent too much administrative time/tasks which lower the general interest. Taking away the administrative burden and merely sending out a holistic message including date, time, meeting link, what and why at once, and offering the possibility to join future events or remain informed even without attending meetings, proves clue to attract attention, lead to success, and can therefore be indicated as a good practice. (See also pages 14-15 on the subgroup 'aging'.)

4. Overall conclusion and future of the Focus Groups

Overall, the pilot initiative of thematic – flagship related – focus groups, is to be considered a success. The initiative has proven that FGs can bridge the gap between different research communities, can create lasting links, and can effectively lead to qualitative (Horizon Europe) project proposals. In effect, the various research communities of the nine ENLIGHT partner universities which did not have much to no mutual collaboration at the start of the ENLIGHT RISE project, have established linkages through the pilot focus groups, clearly leading to important joint research initiatives resulting in numerous submitted and awarded project proposal both at national level as for the prestigious European Horizon Europe framework programme. Proof thereof, the overview in Table 4.1 of the specific outcomes of the focus groups.

In that sense, the choice to deviate from the General Agreement (GA) and immediately start up five focus groups (i.e. one per flagship domain) in project year two instead of gradually one per project year, has proven to be the right decision. Waiting longer would have limited the outcome and jeopardized possibilities of securing more research funding.

Table 4.1 - Overview of notable specific outcome of the pilot focus groups.

Focus Group	Notable specific outcome
Digital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UT-UG joint education and research collaboration - 1 national call proposal submitted (France -> BAIA)
Energy and circular economy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 Horizon Europe CL6 proposals submitted → 1 HE proposal granted (WOODSTOCK) - 1 ENLIGHT 2.0 ETN application
Equity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 4 Horizon Europe CL2 proposals submitted → 1 HE proposal granted (EMMELO) → 1 HE proposal on reserve list (G-ENGAGE) - 1 ERC Synergy proposal in preparation - 1 Horizon Europe CL2 proposal in preparation - 1 ENLIGHT 2.0 ETN application in preparation - 1 joint online workshop held
Health & well-being	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 Horizon Europe (NutriBrain-ERA4Health) proposal submitted - 1 national call proposal submitted → Past to 2nd phase, expecting final result (INNEACH) - 3 ENLIGHT 2.0 ETN applications in preparation - 2 ENLIGHT thematic work groups created - 2 in-person events organised

The success of the pilot initiative did not go unnoticed as it was widely disseminated and presented in relevant fora:

- SwafS in European University Alliances: Cross-Alliances Forum 2023, Brussels (BE), November 30th-December 1st 2023 -> poster session (see annexes 4 and 5 for the poster and the abstract)
- Kick-off EUGLOH BIP "The future of EUGLOH research management", online, March 6th, 2024 -> presentation (see annex 6 for the ENLIGHT RISE presentation)
- EARMA Conference 2024, Odense (DK), 23-25 April 2024 -> discussion table (see annex for the EARMA abstract)

*The most common received appraisal was how the focus groups – and specifically the created spreadsheet – **is an effective low budget tool to map and disclose possible synergies and paths for joint research linked to Horizon Europe funding possibilities.***

A clear challenge for the focus groups is how to stay relevant and attractive once links have been established and results have been achieved. Converting into a mailing list has proven to be a workable and informative solution without the extra administrative burden for researchers.

Attendance and participation to focus groups is, however probably a natural process with a constant fluctuating composition of researchers on the look-out for inter-institutional research contacts at a given point in their career. Once the need has been fulfilled, interest and available time is low. At that point, the partner universities might undertake action to replace members/participants by new members on the lookout for collaboration possibilities.

Hence, the focus groups appear to be something that sporadically gather, e.g. every two years or when a new batch of Horizon Europe calls is launched, whilst intermediately going into hibernation by falling back on occasional informative e-mails messages on possibilities and specific calls for partners.

Finalizing, we would like to highlight again the distillate good practises: the usage of the 'simple spreadsheet', and the straightforward approach within the subgroups.

ANNEXES

Annex 1: Template Participant Profile Focus Group Climate Change

University

Select your Institution.

Department

Mention your department.

Your name
Function

Email: Email address

Bibliography link: Link to publication list, of ORCID/ResearcherID

Key words:

Describe your research expertise in a couple of key words.

Research Focus:

- Short listing of your research interest.

Experience in European or other international projects:

Short list the main relevant EU projects you participated in and your role in the project. If possible add a link to the project website.

When applicable highlight what you can bring into a consortium

Available data, samples or cohorts or relevant papers in the field

List what might be relevant

Available infrastructure - equipment

List what might be relevant

Relevant network contacts

Mention where relevant your network of stakeholders, interest groups, expert panels, societies. Feel free to also add interested colleagues from your university.

What would you like to gain from the ENLIGHT “Climate change” focus group?

What should these online meetings need to offer, so you would partake in them on a regular basis? What should be the short-term or long-term result of these focus groups?

What thematic areas are of interest to you?

List your thematic areas, e.g. urban development – land use – carbon use – socio-ecosystems - biodiversity – environmental behaviour – energy production - etc.

Health Horizon Europe call topics of interest to you

- If you have already identified relevant European calls that are of interest to you, you can mention them here.

Annex 4: Abstract for the SwafS EU-CHARM conference, 30/11-1/12/2023

Creating links and research collaboration through thematic focus groups between EUN partner universities.

Dirk De Cramer and Fede Dewulf

Originally compiled through educational connections, not all partner universities of the ENLIGHT alliance shared close research ties. The ENLIGHT SwafS project (ENLIGHT RISE) therefore strongly focusses – amongst others – on creating joint research links and synergies through R&I capacity building (WP2).

To that intent, one of the instruments created by WP2 are the thematic “*focus groups*”. The objective of these focus groups (FGs) is to i) bring together researchers from all partner universities, ii) identify potential research collaborations, and iii) explore funding opportunities for joint proposals.

Five focus groups have been created, one per focus/flagship domain of the ENLIGHT alliance (Health and Well-being, Digital Revolution and Impact of digitization, Climate change, Energy and Circular Economy, Equity). Each FG started with 3 representatives per partner university: one senior researcher, one junior researcher, and one research support staff member. Jointly, they represent within the FG their institution’s research field on the specific FG focus/flagship domain.

Different approaches were taken by each FG, however, after one semester of activities all FGs are well underway, and all have defined more specific research topics to focus on: some have created thematic subgroups; others focus on specific (Horizon Europe) calls.

What singles out these FGs, is that the researchers are in charge and decide the way to go. We see links and synergies are being created between universities, and individual research networks expanded.

Though the road to successful and sustainable joint research collaboration is still long and finding the suitable modus operandi for every FG proved a real quest, we already consider the FGs a success and a good practice. Eight months of trial and error during the meetings of the FGs has given us certain insights and enables us to draw preliminary conclusions on what works, what doesn’t, good practices, and no-goes.

At the EU-CHARM SwafS event we will share and discuss our experiences with these focus groups, and enlighten how the use of thematic focus groups can bring the research activities at EUN partner universities closer together and incentivise/stimulate joint research collaboration.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035819

Annex 5: Poster for the SwafS EU-CHARM conference, 30/11-1/12/2023

Facilitating new research collaboration and links between ENLIGHT universities through thematic focus groups

Aim

- community building and creation of strong research ties among ENLIGHT partners
- link researchers with focus on specific research domains
- identify potential research challenges as basis for future collaborations
- explore funding opportunities for joint applications with help of the support offices
- strive for successful ENLIGHT grant applications (min. 3 ENLIGHT partners involved)

Composition

- 1 focus group (FG) per ENLIGHT flagship area
 - each FG includes 3 members per partner university (PU):
 - . 1 senior researcher
 - . 1 junior researcher
 - . 1 research support officer (RMA)
- jointly represent the FG's research field within their university's research community

5 flagship areas

Clustering of partner focus / interest & HE calls

Methodology

- Researchers take the lead and decide course of the FG
 - Every FG has a digital environment (SharePoint) + online meeting space (MS Teams)
 - Individual participant profiles
 - Overview of interest and expertise per PU
 - Overview of linked known calls
- PU's indicate what topics they are interested in

spreadsheet of common interest and opportunities for joint collaborations

- topic with high potential form a subgroup where specialist from all PUs:
 - present their research
 - share knowledge, datasets, calls, etc.
 - work on project proposal

Challenges

- Researchers are unfamiliar with representing their institutional research community
- Junior (early career) researchers are harder to involve

Good practice

- The spreadsheet remains as a blueprint of possible (future) collaborations
 - ↳ quick, low-cost and cost-efficient way to identify common research interests
- Subject specific subgroups open to all linked researcher(s) fields attract researchers

Lessons learnt

- It is not imperative for all PUs to participate to all FGs
- The success largely depends on two factors:
 - a strongly motivated researcher taking the lead
 - an RMA supporting the researcher by organising the subgroup

Success – outcomes

- In 10 months already 3 HE proposal consortia
- Joint research and education collaborations
- Joint international workshops

Thematic subgroups of specialists

Annex 6: Presentation for the online Kick-off EUGLOH BIP, 6 March 2024

**FOCUS GROUPS:
OR HOW RESEARCH SUPPORT OFFICERS CAN ENABLE RESEARCH COLLABORATIONS IN EUNs**

ENLIGHT (RISE) Consortium

- 9 comprehensive, research-intensive universities
- Sharing a deep commitment to their social responsibility:

Comenius University Bratislava
Ghent University
University of the Basque Country
University of Bordeaux
University of Galway
University of Göttingen
University of Groningen
University of Tartu
Uppsala University

u^b

ENLIGHT

ENLIGHT FOCUS AREAS

→ 5 Flagship Challenges

- Health and well-being
- Digital revolution and Impact of digitalization
- Climate action
- Energy transition and Circular economy
- Equity

ENLIGHT

ENLIGHT RISE - Horizon2020 SwafS project

AMBITION: become **more competitive and innovative together** & leverage partnerships with our ecosystems to jointly promote a greener, healthier, more equitable and sustainable Europe

ENLIGHT RISE - FOCUS ON RESEARCHERS and THEIR ENVIRONMENT

NEED FOR RESEARCH CONNECTIONS BETWEEN ENLIGHT PARTNERS

- ENLIGHT consortium created based on educational links between partners
- Few (to none) research links various partners
- ENLIGHT RISE therefore strongly focusses – amongst others – **on creating joint research links and synergies** through R&I capacity building
- one of the instruments created by WP2 are **the thematic “focus groups”**.

PILOT FOCUS GROUPS

→ **Aim**

- community building and creation of strong research ties among ENLIGHT partners
- link researchers with focus on specific research domains
- identify potential research challenges as basis for future collaborations
- explore funding opportunities for joint applications with help of the support offices
- strive for successful ENLIGHT grant applications (min. 3 ENLIGHT partners involved)

→ **Composition**

- 1 focus group (FG) per ENLIGHT flagship area
 - each FG includes 3 members per partner university (PU):
 - . 1 senior researcher
 - . 1 junior researcher
 - . 1 research support officer (RMA)
- jointly represent the FG's research field within their university's research community

CLUSTERING OF PARTNER FOCUS / INTEREST & HE CALLS

Methodology

- o Researchers take the lead and decide course of the FG
- o Every FG has a digital environment (SharePoint) + online meeting space (MS Teams)
- o Individual participant profiles
- o Overview of interest and expertise per PU } PUs indicate topics they are interested in
- o Overview of linked known calls

spreadsheet of common interest and opportunities for joint collaborations

- topic with high potential form a **subgroup** where specialist from all PUs:
- present their research
 - share knowledge, datasets, calls, etc.
 - work on project proposal

THEMATIC SUBGROUPS OF SPECIALISTS

LESSONA LEARNT – MID-TERM EVALUATION

→ Challenges

- Researchers are unfamiliar with representing their institutional research community
- Junior (early career) researchers are harder to involve

→ Good practice

- The spreadsheet remains as a blueprint of possible (future) collaborations quick, low-cost and cost-efficient way to identify common research interests
- Subject specific subgroups open to all linked researcher(s) fields attract researchers

→ Lessons learnt

- It is not imperative for all PUs to participate to all FGs
- The success largely depends on two factors:
 - a strongly motivated researcher taking the lead
 - an RMA supporting the researcher by organising the subgroup

→ Success – outcomes

- In 12 months already 6 HE proposal consortia & submitted proposals
- Joint research and education collaborations
- Joint international workshops

“Like a lighthouse guiding sailors to shore, the ENLIGHT alliance will guide students to become lifelong learners and agents-of-change ready to tackle the challenges of tomorrow”

Thank you for your attention
Eskerrik asko zure arretagatik
Bedankt voor uw aandacht
Tänan teid tähelepanu eest
Merci pour votre attention
Vielen Dank für Ihre Aufmerksamkeit
Go raibh maith agat as do aird
Ďakujem za pozornosť
Gracias por su atención
Tack för din uppmärksamhet

Dr. Evi Lippens

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Annex 7: Abstract EARMA Conference, 23-25 April 2024

EARMA Conference Odense 2024

RMA's enabling new research collaborations in EUAs

Creating links and research collaboration between EUA partner universities through thematic focus groups.

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Format: Oral 30 Minutes

Category: 3. Good Practice

Topic: Collaboration and Strategic Alliances

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Reference Number: 909

Abstract

Originally compiled through educational connections, not all partner universities of the ENLIGHT alliance shared close research ties. The ENLIGHT SwafS project (ENLIGHT RISE) therefore strongly focusses – amongst others – on creating joint research links and synergies through R&I capacity building.

To that intent, one of the instruments created are the so-called Focus Groups (FG). The objective of these FGs is to i) bring together researchers from all partners universities active in a specific research domain, ii) identify potential research collaborations, and iii) explore funding opportunities for joint proposals.

Five FGs have been created, one per focus/flagship domain of the ENLIGHT alliance (Health and Well-being, Digital Revolution and Impact of digitization, Climate change, Energy and Circular Economy, Equity). Each FG started with 3 representatives per partner university: one senior researcher, one junior researcher, and one research support staff member. Jointly, they represent within the FG their institution's research field on the specific FG focus/flagship domain.

Different approaches were taken by each FG, however, after one year of activities all FGs are well underway, and all have defined specific research topics within the flagship domain to focus on: some have created thematic subgroups, others focus on specific (Horizon Europe) calls.

What singles out these FGs, is that the researchers are in charge and decide the way to go. RMA's facilitate by alleviating the administrative burden for researchers. We observe that not only do links and synergies emerge between universities, but we also notice the expansion of individual research networks.

Though the road to successful and sustainable joint research collaboration is still long and finding the suitable modus operandi for every FG proved a real quest, we already consider the FGs a success and a good practice. Looking back to a year of trial and error, the online meetings of the FGs have given us certain insights and enables us to draw preliminary conclusions on what works and what doesn't work, and on good practices and no-goes.

At the EARMA conference, we will share and discuss our experiences with these FGs, shedding light on how the use of thematic focus (sub)groups can bring the research activities at EUN partner universities closer together and incentivize/stimulate joint research collaboration. Additionally, we will explore the role RMA's play in this process.